

EUROPEAN POLICYBRIEF

RMROADMAP

CREATING FRAMEWORK CONDITIONS FOR RESEARCH MANAGEMENT TO STRENGTHEN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

Enabling the success of European R&I through a *Roadmap* for Research Management (RM) that supports ERA Action 17 and other objectives of the ERA Policy Agenda.

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INTRODUCTION

Europe's research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem is becoming increasingly complex due to geopolitical tensions, global challenges, and rising societal expectations. Long-term competitiveness in this environment requires not only scientific excellence but also strong and coordinated support from Research Managers (RMs). They play a vital role in maintaining organisation's competitiveness and impact by bridging policy, practice and governance. However, the decentralised and organic development of research management across Europe has resulted in fragmented practices and uneven capacities, while also creating significant opportunities for professionalisation, alignment, and greater interoperability at system level.

To address these challenges, the Research Management Action of the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2022-2024 aimed at the professionalisation of research management by enhancing training and skills development, fostering management competences of researchers and innovators, increasing networking opportunities and promoting institutional and governmental recognition of the profession.

Using a bottom-up, community-driven mobilisation approach, the RM Roadmap project has directly supported these objectives by:

- Developing common terminology for the purpose of definition and segmentation,
- Identifying main challenges, such as gaps in training capacity, funding opportunities and mobility opportunities and exploring potential solutions,
- Formulating an evidence base and a set of policy recommendations for national, regional and local R&I systems,
- Connecting existing European research management networks through an innovative, open co-creation and community building effort

Through these actions, the RM Roadmap has laid the groundwork for the professionalisation of research management, directly strengthening the ERA by enhancing its visibility, capacity, and impact across Europe. The next step is to capitalise on these outcomes and this community to reinforce national, regional, and local R&I systems and to advance interoperability.

The RM Roadmap project combined qualitative and quantitative methods to assess the state of research management across the ERA. Evidence from desk research and large-scale survey with over 2,200 responses was validated and enriched through an extensive co-creation process involving over 140 Ambassadors and engaging thousands of research managers across 40 country communities and 10 thematic communities.

The project confirmed the need for a flexible and inclusive terminology that respects national and regional context but also is accepted at the EU level. The term "Research Manager" has emerged as the most preferred umbrella term and is increasingly recognised in policy discussions. A universally accepted definition has yet to be established, and it must remain adaptable to accommodate evolving roles and emerging fields within the R&I ecosystem. RM Roadmap has facilitated a consensus on a working definition together with the CARDEA project:

Research Managers enable, facilitate, and support the performance of research in all its applications. They hold generalist or specialised roles within the research and innovation ecosystem. Research Managers are based in all types of research performing organisations, including public and private universities, research performing institutes, research funding organisations, medical institutions, NGOs, companies, public authorities, and so on. Research Managers can work as research policy advisers, pre-award and post-award officers, project managers, impact managers, science communicators, financial managers and advisors, legal advisors, contract and compliance managers, data stewards, open science officers, research infrastructure managers and operators, equality, diversity and inclusion advisors, research ethics advisors, knowledge and technology transfer officers, innovation managers and business developers, knowledge brokers, human resource managers in research, AI experts, and leaders of research facilitation offices, etc.

The project's findings highlight several key dimensions that are directly relevant to the Research Management Action of the European Research Area:

- **Educational background and career pathways:** 89% of RM Roadmap survey respondents hold a Master's degree or PhD, yet most enter the field indirectly, without formal RM training. Career pathways are fragmented, with limited leadership roles, often urging RMs to change institutions to pursue advancement.
- **Training and skill needs:** Structured training is essential to ensure continuous professional development, close skill gaps, and foster career progression. While soft skills and transversal abilities relevant for RMs are key, the understanding of the R&I funding landscape and institutional structures is equally vital. Emerging roles, such as open science officers, data stewards, and AI specialists require tailored, role-specific training.
- **Professional development opportunities:** Training opportunities remain fragmented and unevenly distributed, with time constraints as the main barrier. RMs prefer short, modular, interactive, training formats with micro-credentials, while formal certification is often seen as less valuable in the current context due to its limited career impact. RM Roadmap mapped and published available opportunities across Europe.
- **Networks and associations:** Professional associations and sector networks are key for knowledge sharing, peer learning, capacity building, and advocacy and they play critical role in strengthening identity and recognition of the profession.

Co-created by RM Roadmap and CARDEA, the European Competence Framework for Research Managers (RM COMP) was adopted by the European Commission in January 2025. It defines the core skills for effective research management, supporting career development while enabling organisations to align practices with European standards (RM 1–4).¹

¹ The European Commission, with the support of ERA stakeholders, RM Roadmap and CARDEA projects has also created a catalogue of success stories in Research Management, highlighting the value and achievements of RMs across Europe to foster greater recognition and support.

The RM Roadmap project highlights Research Managers' strategic role in enabling research excellence, policy alignment, and institutional resilience. Yet, systemic fragmentation, uneven recognition, and lack of structured support continue to limit their potential. Coordinated professionalisation of research management across the ERA is essential to strengthen national R&I systems and ensure Europe's competitiveness. This is a strategic opportunity to embed RM expertise into organisational and system-level R&I policies, helping address emerging challenges as AI and research security.

The RM Roadmap identifies seven action areas to strengthen national R&I systems:

1. **System-wide dialogue:** RMs are embedded across ministries, RFOs, RPOs, research councils, academic networks and relevant RM associations, yet their role in national policy discussions remains limited, despite being the operational bridge between policy and implementation. Structured engagement is key to address fragmentation and form stronger cross-institutional links, and ensure RMs are involved in shaping reforms aligned with ERA goals.
2. **National assessment of research management:** Significant disparities exist across Europe, particularly in widening countries, where structured training and mobility opportunities remain limited. Comprehensive national assessment of RM roles, legal frameworks, career structures, and capacity gaps is essential for evidence-based reform. With the uptake of RM Roadmap tools, countries can identify roles, frameworks, career structures, and capacity gaps to tailor strategies to local contexts.
3. **Strengthening national connections:** Institutional silos and the lack of formal networks hinder the professionalisation of research management. Across the ERA, many countries lack formal RM associations or rely on volunteer-based initiatives. Collaboration between RFOs and RPOs as well as the establishment of both formal associations and informal communities of practice will support overcoming institutional silos and reduce duplication.
4. **Leveraging EU-level guidance:** Aligning national strategies with EU-level frameworks enhances coherence and interoperability. Embedding RM COMP into HR policies, aligning institutional strategies with ERA objectives, and using tools such as RM Roadmap outputs and other best practices supports harmonising approaches across the ERA.
5. **Stakeholder buy-in and awareness:** Successful implementation requires active engagement of all relevant actors. Tailored communication strategies are essential to highlight the strategic value of research management and secure leadership commitment at institutional and policy levels. Outreach efforts should reflect national and institutional contexts, ensuring inclusive dialogue and positioning research management as a driver of research excellence, impact, and compliance.
6. **Planning national interventions:** Building on assessments, countries can design targeted interventions to address systemic gaps in research management. RM Roadmap results provide essential reflection tools to design targeted actions in upskilling, career development, network building, and advocacy. However, they need to be tailored to national contexts to address systemic gaps. Establishing a national coordination body or task force can ensure sustained dialogue.
7. **Integrating key actors and frameworks:** Creating coordinated actions require the definition of distinct roles of RPOs, RFOs, and national RM associations. Aligning these roles with European frameworks such as RM COMP ensures consistency, interoperability, and a stronger ERA-wide RM ecosystem.

In line with the RM Roadmap results and ERA Action 17, the following recommendations are proposed:

- **Recognition and diversity:** Strengthen the identity and recognition of the RM profession by reinforcing the umbrella term of Research Manager as an inclusive concept, covering the diversity of roles in research management, ensuring equity, and promoting formal recognition of RM as a profession across ERA countries.
- **Professionalisation through structured, inclusive and flexible career frameworks:** Enable multidimensional career path and professional development by adopting RM COMP, improving employment conditions and training offers across all career stages aligned with RM1-4, acknowledging more leadership roles in RM.

- **Tools, resources and systemic collaboration:** Build a more strategic approach through tools, resources and institutional structures that empower Research Managers and enhance Research Support Services. Strengthen partnerships between researchers, leadership, and RM professionals to align RM functions with institutional goals and drive systemic change.

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME	Creating framework conditions for research management to strengthen the European Research Area (RM Roadmap)
COORDINATOR	Nik Claesen, European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA), Brussels, Belgium, nik.claesen@earma.org
CONSORTIUM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA) • European Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (ASTP) • Crowdhelix Limited • The Cyprus Institute • HETFA Kutatointezet KFT • Universidade NOVA de Lisboa • Janssen Pharmaceutical companies of Johnson and Johnson • UNA EUROPA
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WEBSITE	https://www.rmroadmap.eu
FOR MORE INFORMATION	Contact Nik Claesen, projects@earma.org
FURTHER READING	<p>Zsár, V., Balázs, Z., & Koltai, L. (2025). D1.2 Final report on ERA-wide landscape. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16570546</p> <p>Oliveira, C., Dias, F., Trindade, M., Carrapato, A., Varela, C., Hourmat, B., & Delgado, D. (2024). D2.2 Catalogue of existing professional development opportunities. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13829260</p> <p>Oliveira, C., Trindade, M., Carrapato, A., Campelo, D., Hourmat, B., & Varela, C. (2025). D2.3 Report on the professional development opportunities. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16570777</p> <p>Co-creation results: https://www.rmroadmap.eu/co-creation-results</p>

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